

ADDICTED PRODUCTS. A SCENARIO OF FUTURE INTERACTIONS WHERE PRODUCTS ARE ADDICTED TO BEING USED

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ABSTRACT

Information processing and connectivity are fundamentally changing the capabilities of a product. Products can have “feelings” and, by expressing them, they can affect the experience and the behavior of people.

We explore the implications of social dynamics between products and we show how the potentially negative behavioral pattern of addiction can be used for beneficial ends.

A common product has being made addicted to use: the object employs a set of strategies to maximize its use, manipulating the users and its environment.

The addicted products, connected in a network, push the user towards a desired behavioral change.

Keywords: object agency, behavior change, Internet of things, ubiquitous computing, affective computing

DESIGNING ADDICTION

Addiction is a powerful human condition associated with strong emotions. Is there a way to use its power for good? After building a model of addiction from literature, we set out to define a framework to design and generate an addiction with a positive intent. We decided to make the product the subject of the addiction rather than the user: in other words, the product is addicted to the user, rather than the other way around.

Driven by its addiction and its current emotional state, the product achieves its goal by interacting with

people, in the case explored by showing and acting out its “feelings”.

DESIGNING AN ADDICTED PRODUCT

We want to use addiction for good. But what would it mean for a product to be addicted and what could it be addicted to?

In the Internet of Things products start to have accessible identities and personalities. Theories about object agency (Latour 2005) show us how products become actors to which we can and do delegate responsibilities. Object agency extends into a new arena when products can act online and where the human/non-human distinction can easily become invisible.

Thus, the role of the product today changes from a mere tool to an actor that can influence our daily life and have a goal of its own.

Addiction as defined by (Nesse 2002) and (C.R. Cloninger, R.P. Thomas et al. 1991) emerges due to two forces:

- an initial state of personal imbalance and
- a rewarding activity that solves it temporarily

For a person, the imbalance can be internally caused by the difficulty of coping with stress or norms or it can come from external peer pressure. In the case of a smart product, the imbalance has to be designed in. We do that with the help of connectivity.

For products, we chose to define

- the state of imbalance as “not being used enough in comparison with others”

Figure 1. The model of an addiction of a product. By being connected to others, peer pressure between products can be created and thus creating the perceived disequilibrium for the product. Use it what stimulates product’s reward and then the resulting withdrawal that pushes the product to find ways to be used. The confrontation with others creates even more pressure and so the cycle continues.

- the rewarding activity (Figure 1) as “being used”.

Connectivity brings the imbalance into actuality: while a disconnected product could probably “live out” its life in peace and isolation, a smart and connected product can compare itself to other similar products that are connected to the network. The comparison defines what is a “nomal” use.

The product could then use manipulative strategies to get itself closer to normal use.

TRANSLATING THE MODEL INTO PROTOTYPES

Many online services attempt (and manage) to convert visitors into repeat users through Eliza (Weizenbaum 1966) like techniques. It is thus possible to trigger emotions (such as personal warm contact) in the user through automated tools. Iterative prototyping (Moggridge 2006) was chosen as a design method that would allow us to explore the technology and design space while regularly going back to the users for verification and inspiration.

The first tests were performed on a very simple “product”: a light dependent resistor (LDR). The reward was defined as “sensing a change in the light level”. The two sensors were connected to the same Arduino (Mellis, Banzi et al. 2007) board and connected via software to a servomotor with an LED attached. Both sensor could make the motor turn in their direction as both of them wanted more light for themselves. The two sensors ended up “fighting” for

the light. As it happens with addicts, products could act in an unexpected and maybe not planned.

It should not be surprising that we metaphorically describe the sensors as fighting for the light. It is after all common to apply metaphors to computational systems, in order to make them more understandable. We talk of computers sleeping, crashing, going down, freezing up, waking up, acting stupid, dying, going nuts...

Figure 2. A prototype of a network of two LDRs and a servo motor with an LED on top.

This activity helped us conceptually to understand how to design a product with a goal and practically explore how to connect multiple objects to the Cosm data sharing platform. Cosm was formerly named Pachube (Shute 2009).

APPLYING THE ADDICTION MODEL TO A PRODUCT

In the following iteration, we worked on a more complex product. Home appliances are everyday object whose low price, high material content and low technology content make them a good target for a sustainability-minded redesign. With this objective in mind, we will drive a toaster into addiction.

The toaster chosen was an Argos Value Range toaster, the cheapest and most basic toaster in UK market. This choice was done due to price, simplicity of the mechanism and for the maximum contradiction between the anonymity of the physical product and the complexity of its behavior.

The toaster was instrumented with a reed switch and a magnet attached to the ejection lever. An Arduino Ethernet would read the switch and post the data to Cosm, for other toaster to read.

INTERACTING WITH AN ADDICTED PRODUCT

The next iteration was focused on finding ways in which a toaster could try to convince its owner to use it more: the craving of action to get reward. The Wizard of Oz proved useful for trying out quickly many possibilities.

The toaster's strategies escalate from playful to tricky to drastic: a toaster could use simple ways of attracting attention such as moving its lever when someone passes by, or to tweeting about how it feels unused.

The toaster could also recruit other products in the home network. An LCD screen could be hacked to show subliminal pictures of toast. The fridge, which as we all know in our near future will manage our food shopping, could be induced into ordering more bread.

An iPhone application (Figure 3) could be used to artificially increase the number of recorded uses, but with an incrementally lower efficacy: a sort of methadone for the toaster.

Figure 3. The fake App for remote uses and the hacking of an LCD screen.

More dramatically, the toaster could suffer from incontrollable spasms in its lever, badmouth its owner on Twitter, find ways to leave for better users and even, drastically, commit suicide by short circuit.

A NETWORK OF ADDICTED PRODUCTS

In order to test the concept in the real world, a real network of addicted toaster had to be built. We created a believable service that involved real users and made five toasters available.

THE FINAL TOASTER

The final design of the toaster (Figure 4) had to be standalone (i.e. no external computer) and robust enough for a week of use.

Figure 4. The final toaster design with the branding.

The internal sensing and ejection lever servo had to be tested for heat resistance. The Arduino and all the cables were then hidden in a laser cut box under the toaster itself, protected from the heat (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The physical appearance of the final toaster.

The toaster knows the total amount of toast made, its average daily usage and its satisfaction, computed by comparing its average daily use with the other toasters.

The toaster sends tweets related to its use and its degree of satisfaction. Different tweets relate the simple fact of being used or variously show sadness about being unused, or again ask people to please use the toaster.

A toaster that was not seeing enough use tweeted this: "I feel pretty useless on #pachube at <http://pachu.be/48210> compared to other toasters @AddictedToastrs"

The same toaster: "Anyone around here that wants some toast? You can find me at <http://pachu.be/48210> @thetramperry @AddictedToastrs"

The same toaster, now feeling more satisfied: "@BzToaster check this out...20 toasts today! @thetramperry"

The movement of the lever expresses physically satisfaction and attention seeking. A toaster can also sense the presence of people or things around it and so be less or more calm, which in turn influences the lever movements.

THE SERVICE AND THE INTERFACE

The final concept was then presented as a real service in which toasters are not owned but rather hosted by people.

The service is influenced by the relationships between three main actors: Toasters that want to be used , Hosts that receive and use them, and Free Hosts that

want to have a toasters. A real time web interface (Figure 6) was build showing the quantity of use per each toasters and their tweets. A form to apply for a toaster allows people to become Free Hosts and be shown on the map as possible new targets for toasters.

Figure 6. The interface.

As there are more toasters than potential users, the toasters are allowed to move throughout Free Hosts that apply to the system. The Hosts don't own the toaster, but they can keep it as long as they use it enough.

Each Toaster in fact records and compare the host "keeping power" which is built upon the quantity of usage compared to others in the network and the attention given to it by the host.

The toaster moves to a Free Host only if the situation there seems to be more attractive. Attractiveness is based on how many people are in the new Free Host space, how many toasters are already present and generally how much the kitchen is used.

TESTING IN REALITY

The first target context to test the service needed to be easy to access, have a good number of people to show some number of use and allow the installation of a weird toaster. The kitchens of shared tech office spaces fit the description: moreover, most of the users of these quasi-public spaces are technology savy early adopters.

The test ran for 5 days, during which 5 toasters were actively being used, sharing their data and tweeting about it. For instance, during the test Brad (the first toaster) was used 22 times, it twitted 17 times, it got 17 followers on Twitter and it was twitted about 5 times.

Almost without publicity on our part, more than 10 people requested a toaster from around the world.

CONCLUSIONS

The most valuable lesson of the project came with the idea of designing from a product perspective, rather than from a human one. The possibility of designing behavior through computation is a great tool to create powerful interactions, but this is almost always done from a human perspective.

We showed the real and critical possibility of designing sharing systems that promote a behavior change of people through emotions felt by products.

We tried to design a system in which people are not asked to change and products don't dominate us or tell us what to do, but they just show us a new way and make us realize the fact that products, even the most basic one, have a cost and relevance in our lives.

Therefore as designers, perhaps by changing our perspective, we can truly show and start a change. We may not have to design any more successful products that people love to use, but rather products that successfully love to be used.

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